

Optical and electrical studies of thermally stable guest-host polymeric thin films

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Abstract : Guest-host (GH) systems with varying dopant concentrations (2–10% by weight) of 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene as dipolar chromophore (guest) in polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) as host have been made. X-Ray studies have shown them to be non-crystalline. Optical band gap of these GH-systems determined by UV/Vis absorption spectra has been found to be 2.16 eV. Vacuum-deposited thin films of these GH-systems were corona poled under varying conditions of poling temperature as well as poling voltage to probe the optimum concentration possessing highest poling efficiency with good temporal stability of dipolar alignment.

Keywords : Guest-host polymeric thin film, dipolar chromophore.

The development of polymeric materials for nonlinear optics has become an enormous field of research owing to their potential applications in various fields¹. The nonlinear properties of the polymers are related to the delocalized electrons in the conjugated π -electronic states of the polar moieties in the material. These polar moieties consist of electron donor and acceptor substituents connected by highly conjugated system, which promotes charge transfer between the terminating groups. This substitution pattern leads to an asymmetry in the charge distribution in the electronic ground state and hence can introduce a significant polar orientation by aligning polar molecules imbedded in a suitable polymeric matrix by means of high electric field. However, individual molecular contributions in the polymeric film cancel each other due to their random orientation. Therefore, in order to get large nonlinear optical (NLO) susceptibilities, there must be acentric ordering of the chromophores that is commonly achieved by electric field poling using either electrodes or corona discharge poling at elevated temperatures. Corona poling is advantageous because of its simplicity and the fast charging process. In a poling technique, the polymeric thin films are heated and subjected to high DC electric field for certain period of time. After poling for some time the polymeric thin films, still under the influence of electric field, are cooled down to room temperature resulting into poled polymeric samples with noncentrosymmetric alignment of the dipolar chromophores. The dipolar chromophore can be incorporated into polymeric matrix in a number of ways including guest-host (GH) polymers². GH-systems offer several advantages such as ease of preparation and inexpensive

Structure of the chromophore 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene

production of NLO-materials. However, they have poor stability of poling induced alignment of polar moieties. These noncovalently bonded guest-host systems are very advantageous if suitable stability of dipolar alignment can be attained. Hydrogen bonding between host and guest increases the stability of alignment^{2(f), (i)}.

In the present study, the authors have synthesized 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene as dipolar chromophore possessing the requirement of strong donor and acceptor substituents connected by highly conjugated π -electronic system (as shown in the structure [A]). GH-blends, with varying concentrations (2–10% by weight) of 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene (guest) in polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) as host, have been prepared and characterized by IR, UV/Vis spectroscopy, TGA and X-ray techniques. The vacuum deposited thin films of these guest-host blends were used to study their optical as well

Fig. 1. TG thermograms of guest-host polymeric systems.

electrical properties. To optimize the poling conditions, poling efficiencies have been determined by poling these thin films at varying voltages as well as temperatures. The relaxation behaviour of aligned dipoles has also been studied with the help of UV/Vis absorption spectra.

Results and discussion

The IR spectrum of pure guest exhibits O–H stretching frequency at 3280 cm^{-1} . The symmetric and asymmetric stretching bands due to nitro group (pure guest) occur around 1345 cm^{-1} and 1513 cm^{-1} respectively. Pure host (PMMA) shows C=O absorption around 1732 cm^{-1} . The guest-host blends show the absorption bands around 1385 cm^{-1} and 1510 cm^{-1} with very weak intensity due to symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibration of nitro group. O–H stretching vibration in the IR spectrum of guest-host blends occurs around 3250 cm^{-1} (weak intensity). Therefore, guest-host blends O–H frequencies are shifted to lower value compared to that of pure guest (3280 cm^{-1}) indicating the formation of hydrogen bonds between C=O group of host and –OH group

Fig. 2. Variation of order parameter of guest-host polymeric thin films with poling temperature under poling conditions (5 kV, 30 min).

of guest. However, owing to low concentration of guest, absorption frequency of C=O group (PMMA) in guest-host blends almost retains its position.

The thermal characterizations of these GH-blends have been carried out using TGA technique from ambient temperature to $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under N_2 atmosphere. However for better clarity only three thermograms (2, 6, 10%) in the temperature range of $275\text{--}450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are shown (Fig. 1) displaying their high thermal stability. This may be attributed to the formation of hydrogen bonds between hydrogen of hydroxyl group of guest and oxygen of carbonyl group of PMMA (host). TGA thermograms of these GH-blends revealed that their decomposition temperatures (T_d 's) lie in the range $288\text{--}315\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Decomposition temperature of 2% GH-blend is $315\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ where as it is $288\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10%, indicating that their T_d decrease with increase in concentration of guest in PMMA. These values of decomposition temperatures seem to be capable of meeting thermal requirements in constructing optical devices. X-Ray diffractograms of these blends, taken using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation, indicate that these blends possess amorphous structure.

The absorption spectra of the GH-blended thin films exhibited a typical absorption due to the azo-chromophore, with a maximum around 455 nm because of $\pi\text{--}\pi^*$ transition. The noncentrosymmetric alignment of chromophores, essential for the second-order nonlinear optical effect, was achieved by corona poling. Electronic spectral maxima were found to decrease after poling for each dopant concentration due to the dipolar alignment of the chromophores.

Fig. 3. Variation of order parameter of guest-host polymeric thin films with poling voltage under poling conditions ($90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30 min).

The optical energy band gap of guest-host system, 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)-amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene/PMMA was determined using the relation³

$$\alpha = (h\nu - E_g)^{-1/2} \text{ (for direct band gap)}$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ is the incident energy and E_g is the energy band gap. GH-blends possess energy band gap of 2.16 eV.

Since poling is very necessary to get second-order NLO-effects, therefore, poling efficiency must be characterized. To characterize poling efficiency, order parameter (ϕ) was determined using the equation

$$\phi = 1 - A_{\perp} / A_0$$

where A_0 and A_{\perp} are the absorbances of the polymer film before and after corona poling.

To optimize the poling conditions for GH-blended thin films, poling efficiencies were determined by poling these thin films under varying conditions of poling voltages as well as poling temperatures. Poling temperature is one of the principal parameters dictating the optimum polar orientational order in GH-system. The temperature dependence of order parameter was investigated for different dopant concentrations. For each dopant concentration, the order parameter was found to increase with poling temperature under fixed conditions of poling voltages as well as poling time. Fig. 2, showing variation of order parameter with poling temperature for different GH-systems, reveals that these chromophore blended polymeric thin films are more efficiently poled at higher temperature. Under the electric field of 5 kV applied to corona needle for 30 min, the UV/Vis absorbance changes for GH-thin films before and after poling at room temperature (25 °C) are not so large and the order parameter lies within the range 0.151–0.159. This may be attributed to the difficulty of dipolar-chromophore orientation at room temperature. Under the condition of constant poling electric field as well as poling time, the absorbance difference was found to increase with temperature and the maximum absorption difference was observed around 90 °C, thus,

Fig. 4. Current (I)-voltage (V) characteristics of 2% guest-host blend before and after poling under the conditions (5 kV, 90 °C, 30 min).

increasing order parameter to 0.301–0.343. It may be explained on the basis that at higher temperature dipolar-chromophores are free to rotate and hence orientate themselves in proper direction under the applied electric field, thereby decreasing the absorbance and hence increasing the value of order parameter. The decrease of absorbance with poling temperature for copolymer and modified disperse red I/copolymer (guest-host system) has been reported earlier^{2(b)}.

To study the effect of poling voltage on poling efficiency, these chromophore blended polymeric thin films were poled at 90 °C for 30 min under varying poling voltages (2–5 kV) applied to corona needle. Fig. 3, showing the dependence of order parameter with poling voltage, indicates that order parameter increases with increase in poling voltage. The ordering parameters of these polymeric thin films under these conditions were in the range of 0.275–0.343 (Fig. 3), which suggest that these GH-blends are efficiently poled. The increase of order parameter with poling electric field has been reported in the literature for liquid crystalline polymers⁴.

Relaxation behaviour of GH-blended polymeric thin films :

In order to utilize these materials in practical devices, there must be long-term stability of the dipole orientation induced by electric field. However, these dipolar chromophores have tendency to reorient in random direction. Therefore, poling stability must be studied for each GH-system to investigate the optimum concentration of dipolar chromophore suitable for NLO-applications, which can retain the chromophores more efficiently. To probe the orientational stability of the dipolar chromophores in polymeric host, UV/Vis spectra of GH-blended polymeric thin films were studied at different time intervals after poling. The decay of order parameter with

Fig. 5. Effect of various parameters on current (I)-voltage (V) characteristics of guest-host blends poled for 30 min.

time at room temperature for different polymeric thin films poled at (5 kV, 90 °C, 30 min), indicates that these GH-blends possess good temporal stability. Order parameter decay rate is initially high and then almost constant after a certain period of time. Under the poling conditions (5 kV, 90 °C, 30 min), the order parameter decayed by 10.5–13.3% after 5 h of poling and only 6.2–11.9% of its original value in further 245 h. The highest value of order parameter was obtained for 6% GH-system when poled under the electric field of 5 kV at 90 °C for 30 min and that remained upto 0.273 (20.4% decay) after 250 h of poling, again the highest among various GH-systems. Similar relaxation behaviour of these polymeric thin films was found after poling under the conditions (5 kV, 75 °C, 30 min). Since the stability of the orientational order of the NLO-chromophore determines the potential of the system as a second-order NLO-material, these systems (particularly 6% GH-system) seem to be useful for NLO-applications.

Electrical studies of guest-host systems : The electrical nonlinearity of guest-host systems has been studied by comparing their current (I)-voltage (V) characteristics before and after poling. The effect of various parameters such as poling voltage, poling temperature and concentration of guest on electrical characteristics has also been investigated. The vacuum-deposited unpoled guest-host polymeric thin films exhibit linear I-V characteristics for each dopant concentration. Corona poling induced strong electrical nonlinearity in GH-blended thin films by aligning dipolar chromophores. The I-V characteristics of 2% GH-blend before and after poling under the conditions (5 kV, 90 °C, 30 min) are shown in Fig. 4, indicating nonlinear behaviour after poling. The effect of various parameters (temperature, voltage and concentration) on I-V characteristics of guest-host systems poled for 30 min is shown in Fig. 5 (only representative curves are shown for illustration). I-V curves of 6% guest-host system poled under the electric field of 5 kV applied to corona needle at 25 °C and 45 °C indicate almost similar behaviour for -ve field with even order of harmonics. Under the poling temperatures 75 °C and 90 °C, the electrical behaviours are similar, however, no indication of harmonics was observed. In order to investigate the effect of poling voltage, I-V characteristics of 6% guest-host blend poled at 90 °C temperature for 30 min were studied for different poling voltages. Under the electric field of 2 kV, the polymeric thin film indicates second order of harmonics (Fig. 5). The electrical behaviour at 3 kV also exhibits similar characteristics. Poling of the GH-blended thin film under the electric field of 4 kV makes the system to exhibit even order of harmonics. The effect of guest concentration (2–10%) on electrical nonlinearity of the guest-host blends poled under the condition (5 kV, 90 °C, 30 min) is shown in Fig. 5 (curves for 6% and 10% are shown as representative), indicating various orders of harmonics depending on concentration of guest in the host matrix.

Experimental

The detailed procedure for the synthesis of dipolar chromophore 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene has been described elsewhere^{1(a)}.

Different quantities of dipolar chromophore 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene (guest) and PMMA (host) were dissolved in distilled dichloromethane separately followed by mixing to get homogeneous solutions. The chromophore was present in these concentrations : 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10% by weight of PMMA. The solvent was evaporated at room temperature and then the resulting blends were dried on water bath for about 10 h so as to yield 2–10% guest-host systems. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on Buck Scientific M 500 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of GH-blends were performed under nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min on Perkin-Elmer (Pyris Diamond) thermal analyzer from ambient temperature to 800 °C. X-Ray diffractograms were obtained on Bruker AXS model, D8 Advance diffractometer using CuK α radiation from $2\theta = 10^\circ$ to 90° .

Thin films of the guest-host systems, with varying concentrations of guest were grown on the cleaned quartz glass slides by vacuum deposition technique at a vacuum of 10^{-6} mm/Hg with the help of high vacuum coating system (Nirvat EU-300). These thin films were used for studying their optical properties. In the polymeric material, these dipolar chromophores are randomly oriented and hence they cancel out the dipole moment of each other. To produce macroscopic optical nonlinearity, noncentrosymmetric alignment of these chromophores needs to be introduced by electric field poling. The vacuum deposited thin films of different guest-host systems were poled under different poling conditions using optimized high potential multi-point corona poling technique to orient dipolar chromophores in proper direction. The polymeric thin films were heated at various temperatures (25–90 °C) and then a high voltage (2–5 kV) was applied to corona needle, positioned at a short distance (1 cm) above the film surface. Corona poling creates an electric field by generating a discharge from metallic point source and placing a ground behind the film. The intense field generated at the needle tip creates ions with the same polarity as the needle. These gas ions are accelerated toward the film surface and get deposited creating a uniform, high magnitude field across the thin film capable of orienting the dipolar chromophores. The thin films were then cooled down to room temperature under the application of electric field. The optical UV/visible spectra of these thin films were measured before and after poling using a Shimadzu UV-2500 PC spectrophotometer attached to integrated sphere assembly (ISR-240 A). The electrical measurements were carried out with the help of SMU-236 Keithley source measure unit.

Conclusions :

Guest-host polymeric systems possessing good thermal stability with 4-[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]-4'-nitroazobenzene as dipolar chromophore have been prepared and characterized by spectroscopic, thermal and X-ray techniques. The optical band gap of these amorphous GH-systems has been found to be 2.16 eV. Poling efficiency was observed to increase with poling temperature as well as poling voltage. Relaxation behaviour of GH-blended polymeric thin films indicated their suitable temporal stability. The optimum concentration for this particular GH-system has been found to be 6%, which possess highest poling efficiency when poled under the electric field of 5 kV at 90 ° C for 30 min. Poling introduced strong electrical nonlinearity in these polymeric thin films and desired order of nonlinearity may be obtained by varying various experimental parameters.

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